

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF THE THERMO-OXIDATION GRADIENTS IN ORGANIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

Juan P. Márquez Costa¹, E. Monteiro¹ and X. Colin¹

¹ PIMM, Arts et Métiers Institute of Technology, CNRS – UMR 8006, CNAM
151 boulevard de l'Hôpital, F-75013 Paris, France

Email: juan-pablo.marquez_costa@ensam.eu, eric.monteiro@ensam.eu,
xavier.colin@ensam.eu, web page: <https://pimm.artsetmetiers.fr>

Keywords: Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs), Environmental degradation, Interface/interphase, Finite element analysis (FEA)

ABSTRACT

This work outlines the development of a finite element-based numerical tool designed to simulate the thermal aging behavior of epoxy-diamine matrix composites reinforced with continuous fibers under thermal exposition to temperatures below their glass transition temperature (T_g). The approach begins with homogenization technique using a representative elementary volume (REV) that include the fibers, surrounding matrix and interfacial zones around the fibers. Periodic boundary conditions in oxygen (O_2) concentration are applied to numerically determine the effective components of the diffusion tensor for a unidirectional composite. The thermo-oxidation degradation model incorporates a strong coupling between the anisotropic diffusion of O_2 and its consumption by the chemical reaction with the epoxy matrix. The stabilizing effect of carbon fibers in mitigating this degradation is also taken into account. This framework enables the estimation of oxidation gradients across the thickness of the composite sample along its principal directions. The thickness of the oxidized layer (TOL) is calculated from O_2 consumption gradients as recently done for samples of neat epoxy resin. In order to check the robustness of the model and the proposed criterion of TOL detection, the numerical TOL values are compared to experimental measures from literature. The originality of this work lies in the assessment of anisotropic oxidation gradients in composites, particularly by accounting for the crucial role of the fiber-matrix interface and the associated interfacial diffusion in the homogenization calculation.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Thermo-oxidative degradation scenario in Polymer Matrix Composites

Carbon/epoxy composites are widely used in the design of structural parts in the aeronautics sector due to their excellent specific properties. However, their exposure to high temperatures represents a crucial issue to be considered during the design and certification phases of structures. Among the identified risks, thermo-oxidative aging of the matrix plays a particularly decisive role [1]. This phenomenon leads to the formation of an oxidized layer on the surface, causing localized embrittlement and stress and strain gradients likely to cause a catastrophic cracking scenario. Fig. 1 shows the degradation scenario in a thick sample of neat resin by thermo-oxidation. In a first step (between 0 and t_1), the O_2 is consumed while it tries to diffuse in the thickness direction. In a second step (at t_F), the stress and strain fields induced on the surface allow the initiation of a crack, then its propagation in the embrittled zone. Eventually (at t_2), oxidation can cross the oxidized layer/intact core interface to finally progress into the core of the composite, following a progressive damage scenario, and lead to its premature failure [2].

Figure 1. Scenario of crack propagation within a neat resin sample [2].

In the case of a unidirectional (UD) composite reinforced with continuous fibers, the degradation scenario depends on the anisotropy of the composite. The anisotropic oxidation gradients, due to the presence of fibers and interfaces, will lead to heterogeneity of stress and strain fields inducing crack initiation and propagation in the thickness of the oxidized layer (TOL), as shown schematically in Fig. 2:

Figure 2. Scenario of crack propagation within a composite sample. View of a section perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of the fibers

In order to address this complex issue, knowledge of the link between the evolution of the TOL and the degradation of the thermomechanical properties of interest of the composites is essential, before focusing on the critical conditions of crack initiation. For this, the numerical simulation of oxidation gradients proves to be a relevant tool for predicting the value of the TOL. Recent work [3] has shown the robustness of a model developed under finite elements and based on an O_2 balance equation, coupling the diffusion of O_2 and its consumption by the chemical reaction, to predict the TOL in neat resin samples.

Concerning the prediction of oxidation kinetics, it is necessary to consider the anisotropic properties induced by the specific structure of the composites, in particular the anisotropic diffusion of O_2 . In order to propose a relevant model adapted to composites reinforced by continuous fibers, the following question arises: should a specific behavior of the fiber/matrix interface be considered, in particular through interfacial diffusive and reactive terms, to faithfully describe the oxidation gradients of the composites? To answer this question, the article will aim to achieve two objectives. Firstly, it will be a question of: (i) proposing a kinetic model of thermo-oxidation of carbon fiber/epoxy-diamine matrix composites, and secondly: (ii) linking the evolution of the oxidation gradients to that of the TOL in each of the main directions of the composite (1 – fiber direction, 2 – transverse direction and 3 – out-of-plane direction). Thus, the article will be divided into two main parts. First, Section 2 will outline the numerical calculation code developed for composites. Then, Section 3 will compare the numerical simulations of this code with experimental data, in particular with TOL measurements. This last section will conclude on the key role of the fiber/matrix interface. Finally, after a conclusion, perspectives, aimed at predicting the evolution of the thermomechanical properties of interest of composites in the aeronautical field, will be drawn up.

2 MODELING OF OXIDATION GRADIENTS

2.1 Time-dependent kinetics of thermo-oxidative aging

Numerical simulation of oxidation gradients proves to be a relevant tool to predict the evolution of TOL. Recent work [3] has proposed a first numerical calculation code developed under finite elements to simulate the evolution of the oxygen (O_2) concentration in the thickness of neat resin samples. This code is based on the coupling of the two main mechanisms: (i) the diffusion of O_2 and (ii) its

consumption by the chemical reaction. In the case of unidirectional diffusion (e.g. along the thickness of the sample), this equation (Eq. 1) is written:

$$\frac{\partial C(x, t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C(x, t)}{\partial x^2} - r(C(x, t)) \quad (1)$$

$C(x, t)$ being the local O_2 concentration, D the O_2 diffusion coefficient, x the thickness coordinate, and t the time. $r(C)$ represents the rate of chemical consumption of O_2 , the analytical expression of which was determined by carrying out a kinetic analysis of the so-called “closed loop” oxidation reaction. This expression was generalized to the entire family of epoxy-diamine networks [4]:

$$r(C) = 2r_0 \frac{\beta C}{1 + \beta C} \left(1 - \frac{\beta C}{2(1 + \beta C)}\right) \left(\frac{1}{1 + be^{-Kt}}\right)^2 \quad (2)$$

With $\beta = \frac{k_6 k_2}{k_5 k_3 [PH]}$, $r_0 = \frac{k_3^2 [PH]^2}{4k_6}$, and $K = 2(r_0 k_{1b})^{1/2} \left(\frac{\beta C}{1 + \beta C}\right)^{1/2}$, three parameters which are expressed as a function of the elementary rate constants of the oxidation reaction.

The integration with respect to time of $r(C)$ allows direct access to the O_2 consumption gradients:

$$Q(C) = \int r(C) dt \quad (3)$$

On the basis of this quantity representative of the oxidation kinetics, a criterion for estimating the TOL for epoxy-diamine networks exposed to temperatures on either side of their T_g has been validated [3]. This criterion compares the normalised O_2 consumption to the maximal amplitude, as shown in Figure 3 for an epoxy/DDS exposed at 200°C in air:

Figure 3. Normalized oxidation gradients in air at 200°C for an epoxy/DDS. Application of the oxidation criterion to estimate the TOL.

The extension of the previous model to epoxy/carbon composites involves the generalization of Eq. 1 in the 3D domain, considering the anisotropy of the composite. For this, we define the coordinate vector $\mathbf{x} = [x, y, z]$ corresponding to the three orthonormal directions in space. The diffusion/reaction coupling is therefore described according to the following equation (Eq. 4):

$$\frac{dC(\mathbf{x}, t)}{dt} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \nabla C(\mathbf{x}, t)) + r_{UD}(C(\mathbf{x}, t)) \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

\mathbf{D} being the effective anisotropic diffusion tensor (of order 2) and $\nabla C(\mathbf{x}, t)$ the O_2 concentration gradient. $r_{UD}(C(\mathbf{x}, t))$ is the homogenized reactive term in the elementary ply of the UD composite. It is assumed that fibers can chemically play a role in oxidation kinetics, leading to a non-negligible mitigation effect. To consider it, $r_{UD}(C(\mathbf{x}, t))$ can be written as follows to include the stabilizing effect of carbon in the vicinity of the fiber:

$$r_{UD}(C) = 2r_0 \frac{\beta^* C}{1 + \beta^* C} \left(\frac{1 - \varphi}{1 + \varphi/2} - \frac{(1 - \varphi)^2}{2} \frac{\beta^* C}{1 + \beta^* C} \right) \left(\frac{1}{1 + b e^{-K^* t}} \right)^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

$$\text{With } \beta^* = \frac{\beta}{1 + \varphi/2} \text{ and } K^* = k_3 [PH] \left(\frac{k_{1b}}{k_6} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (1 - \varphi)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\beta^* C}{1 + \beta^* C} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

$\varphi = \frac{k_c [Carb]}{k_3 [PH]}$ is the efficiency of stabilization by carbon which, according to reference [5], would be of the order of 10^{-2} to 10^{-1} for certain carbon/epoxy composites. Note that, in the absence of carbon fiber ($\varphi = 0$), we find the reactive term of the neat resin (Eq. 2).

Since the reactive term $r_{UD}(C(\mathbf{x}, t))$ is described at the UD composite scale, it is also valid at the homogenized ply scale. The following section describes the method for homogenizing the components of the effective \mathbf{D} tensor (homogenized at the UD ply scale) using a representative elementary volume (REV) of the composite microstructure (fiber/interface/matrix) and periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) in O_2 concentration.

2.2 Effective O_2 diffusion based on a homogenization approach

Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) are commonly used for representative elementary volumes (REVs) to simulate an infinite and repetitive microstructure of the material. The definition of PBCs ensures that the solution obtained for the REV represents the global behavior of the reinforced composite material. In the case of thermo-oxidation, the boundary conditions must ensure the continuity of the field variable (i.e. C) and its flux (q_C) on the opposite faces of the REV [6]. For this, PBCs must accurately capture the behavior of the composite at the macroscopic scale while resolving the interactions at the REV scale, in particular for the diffusive term affecting the fibers, matrix, and interfaces.

To apply PBCs in C , it is necessary to define a series of equations such that the difference of C between 2 paired nodes is imposed and equal to the macroscopic gradient of C ∇C . As an example, considering the direction d (e.g., x , y , z) of the REV domain, the equation for paired nodes i and j on opposite faces A and B and distanced Δl_d is:

$$C_{j|B} - C_{i|A} = \nabla_d C \Delta l_d = \Delta C \quad (6)$$

With $C_{i|A}$ and $C_{j|B}$ the concentrations at nodes i and j , and $\nabla_d C = \Delta C / \Delta l_d$ the imposed concentration gradient, giving rise to a concentration difference ΔC across the distance between opposite faces Δl_d of the REV in the d direction. The PBCs impose a flow periodicity such that:

$$\mathbf{q}_C(\mathbf{x})|_B = \mathbf{q}_C(\mathbf{x})|_A = -\mathbf{D} \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta l_d} \quad (7)$$

The calculation of the three main components (D_{xx} , D_{yy} , D_{zz}) of the tensor \mathbf{D} requires the performance of 3 calculations by imposing the concentration gradient between each pair of opposite surfaces according to the x , y and z directions. For each direction d , we can write:

$$D_{dd} = \frac{\langle q_{cd} \rangle}{\Delta C / \Delta l_d} \quad (8)$$

$\langle q_{c_d} \rangle$ representing the mean flux within the whole REV volume. The three diffusion components are equivalent to D_{11} , D_{22} , D_{33} in the three principal directions of the UD composite. Table 1 gives the values of the diffusion coefficients of the constituents used for the calculation of the D tensor for two different composites exposed to a temperature of 180°C in air: (a) a simplified epoxy/carbon composite (without fiber/matrix interface) with a fiber volume ratio of $V_f = 0.65$, and (b) an idealized composite (with fiber/matrix interface) with an interphase thickness $h^{interface} = 0.15 \mu m$. It is important to point out that this is a completely realistic interphase thickness, roughly corresponding to the average value of interphase thicknesses reported in the literature for thermosetting matrix composites. The calculations were carried out with Abaqus software. Table 2 shows a synthesis of the results obtained numerically and compared to several analytical laws proposed in the literature [7].

Constituent	Carbon fibre (IM7)	Matrice époxy (ACE)	Interface
D [m ² /s]	0	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Source	Estimated	[3,5]	Estimated*

Table 1. Diffusion coefficients of the different constituents.
 *The fiber/matrix interphase is assumed to be in a rubbery state.

(a) Composite fibre/matrice					
	$\nabla_x C$		$\nabla_y C$		$\nabla_z C$
q_{c_x}					
D_{xx}	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-12}$	D_{yy}	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-12}$	D_{zz}	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-12}$
Analytical [7]					
D_{xx}	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-12}$	D_{yy}	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-12}$	D_{zz}	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-12}$

(b) Composite fibre/interface/matrice					
	$\nabla_x C$		$\nabla_y C$		$\nabla_z C$
q_{c_x}					
D_{xx}	$2.88 \cdot 10^{-10}$	D_{yy}	$3.77 \cdot 10^{-11}$	D_{zz}	$3.77 \cdot 10^{-11}$

Table 2. Results of diffusion coefficients [m²/s] from calculations in the REV with PBCs.

The results obtained clearly highlight the significant effect of the interface on the effective diffusion coefficient, particularly in the longitudinal direction. As often reported in the literature, the fiber/matrix interface of an epoxy matrix composite would be in a rubbery state at the exposure temperature of the composite. Consequently, the oxidation kinetics of the composites described by Eq. 2 must consider this influence of the interface. The following section presents a comparison of numerical simulations of oxidation gradients as well as a confrontation with the TOLs measured experimentally in literature studies.

3 NUMERICAL RESULTS AND COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

Solving the 3D problem presented in Section 2.1 gives access to the evolution of the O_2 concentration gradient $C(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in the three directions of the composite frame. Simulations in air at 180°C for an epoxy/carbon composite of type 977-2/IM7 were carried out for the two composites whose effective diffusion tensor was calculated in Section 2.2: (a) a fiber/matrix composite and (b) a fiber/interface/matrix composite. For each composite, 3 configurations are simulated in order to highlight the oxidation kinetics in each direction: (i) 1 – fiber direction, (ii) 2 – direction transverse to the fibers and (iii) 3 – out-of-plane direction to the fibers.

A criterion was defined for the calculation of the TOL in each direction, as already proposed for neat resin samples [3]. In the case of UD composites, the O_2 consumption gradients ($Q(\mathbf{x}, t)$) are calculated by integrating over time $r_{UD}(C)$, given by Eq. 5. Thus, it is possible to estimate the evolution of the TOL for each of the studied directions (1, 2 and 3). Figure 4 shows the evolution of the TOL for the two types of composites studied: (a) with perfect fiber/matrix interface (i.e. no interface in the modeling) and (b) with idealized fiber/matrix interface (i.e., modeled interphase and assumed to be in a rubbery state). These results were compared with experimental measurements [2], highlighting: (i) the anisotropy of the thermo-oxidation problem of UD composites and (ii) the importance of considering, in the proposed model, the predominant effect of the interphase on the evolution of the TOL, particularly in the longitudinal direction (1 – fiber direction).

Figure 4. Comparison of experimental TOLs (black circles and purple triangles for directions 1, 2 and 3 which are denoted Exp. 1, Exp. 2 = Exp. 3, respectively) to numerical simulations for: (a) fiber/matrix composite (Num. 1 and Num. 2 = Num. 3) and (b) fiber/interface/matrix composite (Num. 1 and Num. 2 = Num. 3).

4 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

A FEM-based model considering the specificities of the diffusion/reaction behavior of UD composites was proposed to describe their thermo-oxidation gradients: the stabilizing effect of carbon fiber and the anisotropic diffusion of O₂ accentuated by a fiber/matrix interphase, assumed in the rubbery state. The reactive term describing the oxidation kinetics at the UD scale has been adapted from neat resin kinetics in order to include a mitigation effect on the oxidation rate induced by the presence of fibers. Diffusion tensor homogenization calculations clearly show the significant effect of the interphase, which was numerically represented by a finite interface at the REV scale. The faster O₂ diffusion in the interphase results in an increase of the effective diffusion coefficient at the UD scale of the order of $< 10^1$ in the transverse directions 2 and 3, and of $> 10^2$ in the longitudinal direction to the fibers 1, directly impacting the TOL values. The comparison of numerical simulations with experimental data allowed to discuss and verify the hypotheses of the literature [2,6] on the non-negligible effect of the interphase, particularly in direction 1.

Future work will focus on other key aspects aimed at completing the general approach to predicting lifetime of composite under thermal aging:

- (i) the experimental validation of the kinetic evolution laws of physicochemical properties (*e.g.*, r_{UD} , \mathbf{D}),
- (ii) the evolution of thermomechanical properties of interest for the aeronautical field (*i.e.*, T_g and elastic properties) and,
- (iii) the integration of these laws into the calculation code to access the gradients of stresses and deformations induced by oxidation, to predict the initiation, then the propagation of cracks in composites.

These steps are necessary to further investigate the coupling between damage and oxidation through a generalized approach in order to predict the lifespan of composite parts based on accurate material thermo-chemo-mechanical degradation criteria.

REFERENCES

- [1] T.K. Tsotsis, S.M. Lee, Long-term thermo-oxidative aging in composite materials: Experimental methods, *Composites Science and Technology*, 32(11), 1998, pp. 1115-1135 (doi: [10.1016/S0266-3538\(97\)00123-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(97)00123-1)).
- [2] X. Colin, A. Mavel, C. Marais, J. Verdu, Interaction between cracking and oxidation in organic matrix composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **39(15)**, 2005, pp. 1371-1389 (doi: [10.1177/0021998305050430](https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998305050430)).
- [3] J.P. Marquez Costa, X. Colin, Finite element modelling of the oxidation gradients of epoxy-diamine matrices below and above their glass transition temperature, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **234**, 2025, pp. 111194 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2025.111194](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2025.111194)).
- [4] X. Colin, F. Essatbi, J. Delozanne, G. Moreau, A new analytical model for predicting the thermal oxidation kinetics of composite organic matrices. Application to diamine cross-linked epoxy, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **186**, 2021, pp. 109513 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2021.109513](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2021.109513)).
- [5] X. Colin, C. Marais, J. Verdu, Kinetic modelling of the stabilizing effect of carbon fibres on thermal ageing of thermoset matrix composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **65**, 2005, pp. 117-127 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2004.06.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2004.06.009)).
- [6] K.V. Pochiraju, G.P. Tandon, G.A., Schoeppner, Evolution of stress and deformations in high-temperature polymer matrix composites during thermo-oxidative aging, *Mechanics of Time-Dependent Materials*, 12(1), 2008, pp. 45-68 (doi: [10.1007/s11043-007-9042-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11043-007-9042-5)).
- [7] T. Peret, A. Clement, S. Freour, F. Jacquemin, Homogenization of Fickian and non-Fickian water diffusion in composites reinforced by hydrophobic long fibers: Application to the determination of transverse diffusivity, *Composite Structures*, **226**, 2019, pp. 111191 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.111191](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.111191)).